

GOOD PRACTICES THAT PROMOTE RESPECT FOR NATURE AMONG THE YOUNG

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Abstract:

The "Aurel Vlaicu" Theoretical High School, a partner institution with Valahia University in Targoviste within the CONNECT Project, promotes the transition towards an ecological, healthy and sustainable lifestyle by maintaining a clean environment, taking responsibility for pollution prevention and resource management without endangering the natural balance of the planet. The young generation needs examples of good practices, because they gain motivation, openness to cooperation, communication and a positive attitude towards nature.

The realization of activities by students together with teachers, parents and other members of the community, is an effective way to consciously do ecological education through which part of the local environmental problems can be solved, with a positive impact at the macro-regional level.

Keywords: *positive attitude towards the environment, ecological education, practical activities.*

"Aurel Vlaicu" Theoretical High School is the largest school unit in Prahova county, coordinating 6 kindergartens, 4 primary and secondary school and high school structures, spread over the entire area of Breaza. About 1600 students learn in a stimulating and collaborative environment.

The following participated in the CONNECT Project: approximately 300 students from all levels of education, 25 teachers, parents, members of the local community.

Involving students in community life through environmental projects aims to form an ecological behavior that helps to complete the personality and consciousness of future citizens.

Objectives:

- 1.The need to adopt an ecological behavior both in students and at the level of the society in which they live .
- 2.Bringing man into a position to respect the values of nature and the environment in which he lives.
3. Substantiating environmental education through the power of example.
4. Developing an active community of students who promote respect for nature.

Within the theme proposed by the CONNECT Project "Biodegradable plastics – a solution for white pollution", the following activities were carried out: popularization of the project theme, environmental questionnaire, greening, planting,

and selective plastic collection campaigns, debate, research activities, products of students.

Using Google's Classroom platform, we created a class called Connect with Science for better collaboration, we uploading materials to the classroom, viewing materials on plastic recycling and solving tasks for students (fig.1)

Figure 1. "Connect with Science" on Google's Classroom platform.

In a first stage, we applied an environmental questionnaire to identify the degree of information and awareness on plastic pollution. The questionnaire was answered by six hundred and eighty-two respondents, of whom about forty-one percent represented parents or teachers, the rest being students. To the question What do you understand by protecting the environment? five hundred and eighty-six people responded to protecting nature and two hundred and sixty-seven answered cleaning. 91% of people agreed that human activities influence environmental quality. When asked what is the biggest problem facing our planet, 37% answered improper waste disposal, other thirty-seven percent answered lack of involvement in waste reduction, and twenty-five percent answered throwing packaging on the ground. We asked what is the source of information on environmental protection and 61% replied from internet, 38 % replied from TV, radio, 29% replied from extracurricular activities. At the question Who should care about protecting of environment? 83% replied every citizen, 38% local authorities, 11% believes that schools should be concerned about environmental protection. Consider efforts to reduce environmental pollution in your city to be satisfactory and effective? and 50% answered yes. We ask if a correct attitude towards the environment leads to an increase in the quality of life and 55% of respondents believe that a correct attitude towards the environment would considerably improve their quality of life.

Other activities carried out within the CONNECT Project:

✓ Greening activity in Constantin Brancoveanu Park-an emblematic place for the Breaza town (fig.2)

Figure 2. Greening activity in Brancoveanu park.

✓ Planting activity in the schoolyard (fig. 3): our students planted flowerbeds in the school yard, thus practicing their gardening skills while also contributing to the beautification of the playground.

Figure 3. Planting activity in the school yard.

✓ Arrangement of a solarium in the kindergarten yard where students can observe morphological changes that occur at different stages of plant growth(fig. 4).

Figure 4. Gardening activities in the solarium in the kindergarten yard.

✓ Selective collection of plastic for recycling. We initiated the campaign in school

with the title: "*Inspire students in your school to go plastic free.*" With the help of a parent who sponsored the school with the purchase of five bins, we were able to selectively collect the plastic. Breaza City Hall then took care of transporting it to a plastic recycling company. As a result of this activity, students noticed a 12% reduction in single-use plastic packaging used in school in a week.

✓ In philosophy class, students debated the topic of environmental pollution. For example at the question Should developed and developing countries be subject to the same constraints in terms of pollution standards? The pro argument on this topic was that It is normal for these constraints to apply to all states because people, being consumers, through their activities pollutes the environment. The contra argument on this topic was that constraints are not strictly about implementation their micro-level (individual level) and weak states developed need financial support to be able to cope with these constraints.

✓ Also, within the CONNECT project we carried out a series of research activities. Using the lab experiment, the students obtained biodegradable plastic and used it to plant parsley seeds. After about a month after planting, the plant can be observed (fig.5).

Figure 5. Obtaining biodegradable plastic.

✓ The students made a case study with the topic Chewing gum contains plastic or not. Research has found that chewing gum contains plastic and can therefore be recycled. In England there are containers on the street in which chewing gum can be recycled, called GUM-DROP. The plastic obtained from recycled gum is called GUM-TEC and is used to make various objects.

✓ Flyers, posters, advertising spots, plastic decoration and literary creations- within these activities, the students demonstrated their creativity and developed various skills (fig. 6, 7).

Figure 6. Flyers, „White pollution”.

Figure 7. Plastic decoration.

The impact of this activities: incorporating skills-development into your classroom activities can stimulate students to reduce the use of plastics in their own life. Many students take the message home to their families and try to reduce plastics together. Modelling behaviours is a great way to quietly reinforce simple solutions for living plastic free.

Ecological education will reach its true goal only when the students - the citizens of tomorrow - will be convinced of the necessity of protecting nature and will become decision-making factors in the action of reconciling man with nature. Aware of the co-evolution with nature, the health of the local environment, students will understand the usefulness of these practical actions to care for and protect the environment.

Group discussions and messages collected from the target group (children, parents, teachers, members of the local community) reinforce our belief that such projects capitalize on the immense potential of children and teachers who can turn such activities into successful experiences.

Conclusion:

The activities proposed by CONNECT Project, promotes the transition towards an ecological, healthy and sustainable lifestyle by maintaining a clean environment, taking responsibility for pollution prevention and resource management without endangering the natural balance of the planet.

The young generation needs examples of good practices, because they gain motivation, openness to cooperation, communication and a positive attitude towards nature.

The inter- and transdisciplinary activities within the CONNECT Project allowed an integrated approach centered on real facts, on relevant aspects of daily life, presented as they affect and influence our lives.